

Symbolic Explainer of Power System Dynamics

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Abstract—Power systems face increasing uncertainties that create nonlinear regime-dependent dynamics. Critical Clearing Time (CCT) remains a key transient stability metric, yet analytical relations with operating conditions are rarely tractable. Advanced machine learning techniques offer accurate CCT prediction and partial interpretability, but fail to uncover the governing functional dependencies. This paper introduces a Piecewise Symbolic Regression (Pc-SR) framework that automatically discovers regime-conditioned equations linking system variables to CCT. Pc-SR combines cost-complexity-pruned decision trees for task-aware partitioning with symbolic models in each region. Validation on synthetic data confirms recovery of correct partitions and equations under noise, while tests on single-machine infinite-bus variants rediscover analytical CCT equations. Applied to a modified 39-bus system with inverter-based resources, Pc-SR produces interpretable, regime-specific CCT surrogates matching black-box accuracy while exposing nonlinearities and interactions. This framework advances beyond descriptive explainability, providing transparent models to accelerate stability screening and support operator insight into complex dynamic behaviors.

Index Terms—Symbolic Regression, Transient Stability, Interpretability, Artificial Intelligence.

I. INTRODUCTION

The ongoing transformation of power systems, driven by the rapid growth of inverter-based Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) and the retirement of conventional power plants, has profoundly altered power system dynamics and introduced new layers of complexity. Operators, who have long relied on offline dynamic simulations to extract insights and develop heuristics, now face increasingly nonlinear and time-varying behaviors shaped by distributed controls. Among the affected phenomena, transient stability remains a critical concern, with the Critical Clearing Time (CCT) serving as a fundamental stability indicator. However, in realistic multi-machine grids, it

can only be obtained through computationally intensive time-domain simulations of nonlinear differential-algebraic models. Analytical relations linking CCT with system parameters are only tractable under strong simplifying assumptions, such as classical generator representations without excitation or control systems, which limit their applicability to practical large-scale networks.

Machine learning (ML) techniques have recently been explored to accelerate dynamic security assessment by learning mappings between power system variables and stability indicators [1]. While such models can achieve high predictive accuracy, they often act as “black-boxes” that limit transparency, trust, and interpretability in operational settings. Simple models (e.g., decision trees or linear models) are inherently more transparent, but typically lose accuracy in complex nonlinear domains; this interpretability-accuracy trade-off is well known in ML theory [2]. Post-hoc explainable Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods, such as SHAP (based on Shapley values), can leverage highly accurate models and mathematically grounded game-theoretic principles to attribute importance to individual variables [3]. However, they remain descriptive and do not uncover the governing functional dependencies.

Within the broader field of *symbolic AI*, which aims to combine data-driven learning with human-readable reasoning, Symbolic Regression (SR) [4] provides a very promising direction. By discovering explicit analytic expressions from data, it enables compact, transparent surrogates that reveal nonlinearities, interactions, and sensitivities, restoring interpretability and enabling rapid what-if reasoning in dynamic studies. Despite its potential, and recognized application in numerous scientific fields [5], its use in the power systems domain remains limited. Early symbolic learning efforts in this direction used gene expression programming to derive interpretable rules for transient stability classification, outperforming neural network approaches on standard IEEE systems [6]. Authors in [7] extended the Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics framework to power system dynamics, coupling it with the Manifold Boundary Approximation Method for information-geometric model reduction. Their approach refines Synchronous Generator (SG) differential-algebraic equations from transient data, showing that sparse symbolic models can capture key nonlinear couplings and improve the interpretability of transient stability analysis. SR

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was also applied in electricity markets to evolve adaptive bidding strategies, allowing agents to autonomously learn and adjust profitable behaviors in competitive double auctions [8]; in AI-assisted power converter design, allowing reinforcement learning agents to automatically generate and refine circuit topologies that maximize efficiency based on user-defined specifications [9].

However, the dynamics of realistic power systems are inherently *piecewise*, i.e., the stability mechanisms can shift abruptly with control modes or SG capacity levels. A single global analytical formula cannot adequately capture these regime changes, leading to dense and unreliable expressions. Piecewise modeling is therefore essential to isolate locally consistent behaviors and produce interpretable equations valid within specific operating regimes. Only a handful of studies have proposed piecewise extensions: clustering-based SR [10], hierarchical cooperative genetic programming [11], PS-Tree [12], and unified optimization frameworks [13]. While these works highlight the potential of combining partitioning with symbolic modeling, persistent challenges remain: (a) unsupervised partitions that do not reflect physical regimes, (b) volatile decision boundaries, (c) opaque evolved conditions, and (d) limited scalability to noisy high-dimensional datasets. Related efforts such as the Evolving Symbolic Model (ESM) [14] illustrate the value of symbolic structures to support human decision-making. However, in ESM the region partitioning and symbolic models are obtained from a single symbolic solver, whereas the present framework adopts a principled partition–equation co-optimization. This approach delivers simple equation systems for each region of the operating space, even for large-scale systems. This facilitates a clear understanding of the system dynamics in each region and ensures good local interpretability.

This paper introduces a principled *piecewise SR* (Pc-SR) framework specifically designed for transient stability analysis. Pc-SR combines cost-complexity–pruned Regression Decision Trees (RDTs) for task-aware partitioning with local SR models in each region, yielding a compact set of regime-specific equations that link system variables to stability margins and can be directly interpreted by operators to enhance situational awareness. The main original contributions are:

- A novel method that integrates SR with pruned RDTs to automatically identify regime-dependent dynamic behaviors in power systems.
- A multi-objective selection strategy that jointly manages the trade-off between model interpretability and accuracy by identifying the smallest tree yielding accurate and parsimonious SR models across multiple regions.
- A post-hoc region-merging procedure based on symbolic and embedding-based equation similarity, improving model compactness and interpretability.

The proposed Pc-SR method was (a) validated on a synthetic benchmark with a planted regime structure and on two simplified Single-Machine Infinite-Bus (SMIB) system variants, for which the analytical CCT equations are exactly recovered, and

(b) tested on an adapted 39-bus system incorporating inverter-based DERs within a 50-dimensional feature space, characterized by varying SG capacity levels. The method achieved black-box-level accuracy while maintaining full transparency. By producing regime-conditioned SR surrogates, it advances explainable AI for power system dynamics, moving beyond descriptive feature attributions toward interpretable functional models that are consistent with observed physical behavior.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the proposed methodology and describes its main components. Section III presents validation tests on benchmark systems to assess the method’s ability to accurately identify operating regimes and recover analytical ground-truth expressions. Sections IV and V apply the proposed framework to a realistic 39-bus power system, analyzing the derived results and their physical interpretation. Finally, Section VI summarizes the main findings and outlines directions for future research.

II. PIECEWISE SYMBOLIC REGRESSION FOR TRANSIENT STABILITY ASSESSMENT

The proposed methodology, Pc-SR (Section II-A), automatically discovers interpretable operating regimes by fitting SR models within regions defined by a RDT (Section II-B). RDT is chosen as: (a) it yields task-aware partitions guided by the target variable, unlike unsupervised clustering, (b) it generates clear “if–then” rules based on individual feature thresholds, often corresponding to meaningful engineering regimes, and (c) through the Cost-Complexity Pruning (CCP) path, it spans partitions from simple to complex, enabling selection of the smallest tree that supports accurate, low-complexity formulas. For clarity, Figure 1 conceptually depicts the proposed methodology through a simple example that demonstrates the workflow discussed in this section and its corresponding expected outcome.

The choice of the pruned tree along the CCP path is formulated as an optimization problem, where the partition is selected using a combined score that balances multiple objectives (Section II-D). In particular, the criterion evaluates the symbolic models trained within the leaves of each candidate tree, and is designed to select the partition for which their average accuracy, worst-case behavior, and regional balance are jointly acceptable. In this sense, the method purposely explores some degree of over-segmentation, but only retains the partition size beyond which accuracy does not significantly improve while symbolic equations remain reasonably compact. Each leaf, therefore, corresponds to an interpretable rule-based region that is well suited for subsequent SR modeling. This iterative process is schematically illustrated in panel (1) of Fig. 1.

The final step is the merging of redundant regions based on the similarity of their symbolic equations (Section II-E). While the RDT partitions provide rule-based interpretability, they may introduce unnecessary fragmentation. As illustrated in panel (2) of Fig. 1, by comparing regional models through both embedding similarity and exact symbolic checks, we

consolidate equivalent regimes. This merging ensures that the final Pc-SR representation is compact, interpretable, and free from redundant regions, as seen in panel (3) of Fig. 1.

A. Problem framing

The goal is to approximate a potentially non-smooth mapping $f : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ (CCT) by a piecewise SR model (Pc-SR):

$$\hat{f}_\alpha(x) = \sum_{\ell=1}^{L(\alpha)} \mathbf{1}\{x \in \mathcal{R}_\ell^\alpha\} g_\ell^\alpha(x), \quad \mathbf{1}\{x \in \mathcal{R}_\ell^\alpha\} = \begin{cases} 1, & x \in \mathcal{R}_\ell^\alpha \\ 0, & x \notin \mathcal{R}_\ell^\alpha \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denotes the input feature vector, and \mathcal{R}_ℓ^α are regions defined by feature-threshold rules induced by a pruned RDT with CCP parameter α ; in each region, a compact symbolic model g_ℓ^α is fitted. The symbols in (1) represent:

- \hat{f}_α : the overall piecewise predictor at pruning level α ;
- $L(\alpha)$: number of leaves in the tree at pruning level α ;
- \mathcal{R}_ℓ^α : the ℓ -th region from that pruned tree;
- g_ℓ^α : regional symbolic model trained on samples in \mathcal{R}_ℓ^α .

B. Partitioning model: cost-complexity-pruned RDT

In Pc-SR, the regions represent subsets of the operating space where the relationship between system variables and the CCT can be captured by a simpler functional equation. In large-scale power systems under significant variability, the dependence of CCT on dispatch, load, and DER behavior changes abruptly across operating regimes—for instance, under different SG capacity levels. A single global equation may suffice within a narrow range of operating points, but across such mixed regimes it would become overly complex or misleading. Pc-SR therefore partitions the operating space into locally homogeneous regions where compact and interpretable SR models can be derived.

These regions (leaves) are obtained from a RDT trained with explicit controls on model complexity and minimum data requirements per leaf. The framework begins by fitting a *base tree* of moderate depth (typically 8–12) while enforcing a minimum number of samples per leaf (e.g., 50). These values follow empirical heuristics: the minimum sample constraint avoids brittle or unstable SR models that would otherwise arise from regions with too few training points. In higher-dimensional settings, small leaf sizes become increasingly risky, as the local SR model must capture relationships across more variables and therefore requires stronger data support. The chosen depth provides a balanced starting point—very shallow trees may under-partition nonlinear behaviors, whereas excessive depth can yield unstable or data-sparse leaves. The *base tree* represents the most complex candidate partition considered in the framework.

To explore simpler partitions, we apply CCP, which yields an ordered sequence of pruning parameters $\{\alpha_k\}$ where branches are successively collapsed. Larger values of α correspond to simpler trees (fewer leaves). The set $\{\alpha_k\}$ is obtained using scikit-learn’s `cost_complexity_pruning_path`,

which returns the effective alphas at each pruning step (i.e., where the optimal subtree changes) [15]. To limit runtime, the number of candidate α values is capped to a fixed budget (e.g., 10–50), depending on the complexity of the underlying problem.

Notably, a RDT of depth 10 can theoretically generate up to $2^{10} = 1024$ leaves, representing an extremely fine segmentation of the input space. In practice, this upper bound is never reached due to the enforced minimum-sample-per-leaf constraint and the bounded CCP path, which together prevent excessive fragmentation. For datasets of moderate size (e.g., 4000–5000 samples), these structural controls naturally yield shallower effective partitions while preserving regime expressiveness. These parameters remain tunable and can be adjusted to the dimensionality and complexity of the studied system.

This procedure results in a principled family of nested partitions, each of which satisfies minimum sample-size guarantees while varying in granularity. In subsequent steps, SR models are trained within each leaf, and the best partition is selected according to a multi-objective score. The use of CCP thus ensures that Pc-SR explores a small yet diverse set of candidate trees, providing a stable basis for downstream SR. From an algorithmic perspective, the CCP path offers the additional advantage that many leaves remain unchanged across successive prunings. This property enables caching and reuse of the corresponding symbolic expressions, substantially reducing the number of PySR runs—a critical improvement given the computational cost of repeated equation discovery.

C. Regional symbolic regression models

For each leaf ℓ of a candidate partition (i.e., the tree at pruning level α), a compact symbolic regressor g_ℓ is fitted on $x \in \mathcal{R}_\ell$ using the PySR package [5]. The purpose is to obtain a local model that is both accurate and interpretable, capturing the behavior of the target variable within a homogeneous region.

To enforce interpretability and reduce runtime, the search space is deliberately constrained and tailored to the anticipated functional forms of the problem. A minimal set of binary operators ($+$, $-$, \times , \div) together with a few unary operators (e.g., \log) is allowed. These can be adjusted depending on the application, while pathological nesting patterns (e.g., $\log(\log(\cdot))$) are explicitly forbidden. The search is further regularized by imposing a modest iteration budget and a strict cap on maximum expression size (e.g., 10–20 nodes), ensuring that the resulting equations remain compact and interpretable. Although these limits may vary across problems, the guiding principle is to favor low-complexity formulas over highly intricate expressions.

Each fitted model is summarized by three key diagnostics:

- 1) the recovered equation string,
- 2) its symbolic complexity (number of nodes), and
- 3) the per-leaf mean squared error (MSE_ℓ), together with the full distribution of per-sample squared errors (e_i^2).

(1) Iterate along CCP path (characterized by $\{\alpha_{kj}\}$):

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the methodology, illustrated through a simple case.

(2) Post-Hoc Merging

(3) Interpretable rule based model

This design allows learning of separate, physically meaningful expressions for each region. Because the regions are defined to be homogeneous with respect to the target variable, the resulting formulas are typically both accurate and interpretable, with signs and functional structures that align with domain-specific engineering expectations.

D. Candidate scoring and selection

Each candidate tree (defined by a pruning parameter α) is paired with symbolic models trained in its leaves. To select the most suitable partition, the candidates are evaluated using three complementary metrics:

1. *Global accuracy.* The first metric is the global MSE, expressed as a sample-weighted average of per-leaf MSEs:

$$MSE(\alpha) = \sum_{\ell=1}^{L(\alpha)} w_{\ell} MSE_{\ell}, \quad w_{\ell} = \frac{n_{\ell}}{n}, \quad (2)$$

where $MSE_{\ell} = \frac{1}{n_{\ell}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{R}_{\ell}^{\alpha}} (g_{\ell}^{\alpha}(x_i) - y_i)^2$ is the MSE in leaf ℓ , n_{ℓ} its sample size, n the total number of samples in the dataset, and y the true value of the target. It reflects overall predictive accuracy while preventing large leaves from dominating unfairly.

2. *Tail risk.* To guard against rare but potentially significant errors, the Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR) of the squared errors is computed at confidence level β ($\beta = 0.95$) [16]:

$$CVaR_{\beta}(\alpha) = \mathbb{E} [e_i^2 | e_i^2 \geq VaR_{\beta}], \quad e_i^2 = (\hat{f}_{\alpha}(x_i) - y_i)^2 \quad (3)$$

This penalizes the worst $(1 - \beta)$ fraction (i.e., 5%) of errors, ensuring that candidate partitions do not hide large failures that the global MSE might smooth over. Such safeguards are especially important in operational settings.

3. *Leaf-level imbalance.* Finally, the balance of performance across regions is measured using a weighted L^p mean of per-leaf MSEs:

$$LeafLp(\alpha) = \left(\sum_{\ell=1}^{L(\alpha)} w_{\ell} MSE_{\ell}^p \right)^{1/p}, \quad w_{\ell} = \frac{n_{\ell}}{n}. \quad (4)$$

With $p > 1$ ($p = 4$), ill-fit leaves contribute disproportionately more to the score than under a simple average. As $p \rightarrow \infty$,

the measure approaches the maximum leaf MSE, enforcing a “no bad leaves” stance. This nudges the algorithm toward partitions where performance is uniformly acceptable across leaves, complementing the sample-level protection of CVaR.

Composite score and optimization. Since these three metrics may differ in scale, each is normalized by its ratio to a robust best value (e.g., the minimum or a low-percentile reference) [17]. The minimum value across the evaluated α values is selected. The composite score is then defined as

$$S_w(\alpha) = w_{MSE} \widetilde{MSE}(\alpha) + w_{CVaR} \widetilde{CVaR}_{\beta}(\alpha) + w_{Lp} \widetilde{LeafLp}(\alpha), \quad \sum_i w_i = 1, \quad w_i \geq 0, \quad (5)$$

where $\widetilde{\cdot}$ denotes normalized metrics. Weights $w = (0.5, 0.3, 0.2)$ are adopted to prioritize average accuracy while retaining explicit safeguards against tail errors and unbalanced partitions. Sensitivity to score weights was assessed by performing a sweep over the weight simplex ($w_{MSE}, w_{CVaR}, w_{Lp}$) and repeating experiments across different feature subsets, minimum number of samples per leaf and RDT random seeds. In particular, for the power system problem, feature sets ranging from 30 to 60 variables were considered, together with minimum samples per leaf values between 50 and 100, and five different RDT random seeds.

Let A denote the set of candidate α values along the CCP path. The optimal pruning parameter α^* is the one minimizing $S_w(\alpha)$ across the candidate set, as in (6).

$$\alpha^* = \arg \min_{\alpha \in A} S_w(\alpha) \quad (6)$$

Final selection and stopping criteria. To avoid overfitting, the following simplicity-bias rule is applied: if multiple candidates lie within 5% of the best composite score, the simplest tree (fewest leaves) is selected. The parameter ultimately chosen under this rule is denoted by α^{\dagger} . Scanning along the CCP path is terminated if an acceptably low score is reached early or if a fixed budget of candidate α values is exhausted. The guiding principle is not to find the deepest tree, but rather to identify the simplest partitioning that allows for accurate SR in every region.

However, this partition may still contain regions that are unnecessarily fragmented, as two neighboring leaves can sometimes produce SR models that are algebraically or functionally

equivalent. This means they might belong to one unified regime. To address this, a post-hoc merging stage, described in Section II-E, is introduced.

E. Post-hoc merging of regions

The post-hoc merging stage consolidates regions whose symbolic regressors are effectively equivalent. Equivalence is established through a combination of canonicalization, structural checks, embedding-based similarity, and numerical validation. This procedure ensures that distinct regimes are preserved while redundant partitions are eliminated.

Pairs of regional models are compared, and leaves/regions are merged whenever their symbolic expressions are found to be equivalent. The comparison proceeds in stages:

1. *Canonicalization.* To reduce false mismatches in the embedding space and speed up comparisons, expressions are first canonicalized into a consistent symbolic form prior to similarity checks. The canonicalization pipeline, implemented in Python and leveraging SymPy’s algebraic manipulation capabilities [18], consists of:

- **Parsing:** convert strings to SymPy expressions (`sympify`).
- **Normalize divisions:** rewrite $x/0.5$ as $x \cdot 2.0$.
- **Round floats:** enforce consistent precision.
- **Explicit multiplicative form:** ensure variables appear as $1.0 \cdot x$ to avoid false similarity score between identical expressions (e.g., x vs. $1.0 \cdot x$).
- **Simplification:** apply algebraic rules (e.g., $x + x \rightarrow 2x$) using `simplify` from SymPy.

For embedding comparisons only, variables are renamed to a standardized schema (x_1, x_2, \dots) to prevent spurious mismatches due to naming conventions (e.g., $DP25$ vs. δ_5).

2. *Structural checks.* Each expression’s variable and operator sets are extracted and compared for quick structural compatibility. If either set differs, the pair is deemed non-equivalent.

3. *Embedding similarity.* For structurally compatible pairs, canonicalized expressions are embedded using a pre-trained sentence transformer (all-MiniLM-L6-v2) [19]. Since the model was trained primarily on natural language, it does not perform symbolic reasoning. Instead, embeddings reflect textual similarity between the string representations of expressions. This step therefore acts as a heuristic filter: expressions that look linguistically similar (e.g., $2 \cdot x_1 + \sin(x_2)$ vs. $1.99 \cdot x_1 + \sin(x_2)$) will yield higher cosine similarity, while clearly different expressions (e.g., $x_1 + x_2$ vs. $\sin(x_1)$) will not. Cosine similarity is computed in embedding space, and merging decisions are made according to a strict ($\tau_{\text{strict}} = 0.9$) and a loose ($\tau_{\text{loose}} = 0.8$) threshold:

- If similarity $\geq \tau_{\text{strict}}$, the regions are merged directly;
- If $\tau_{\text{loose}} \leq \text{similarity} < \tau_{\text{strict}}$, the pair is flagged for further numerical validation;
- If similarity $< \tau_{\text{loose}}$, the pair is discarded as non-equivalent.

The thresholds were chosen empirically (tested under multiple expressions) to balance two risks: setting them too high would

miss genuinely equivalent expressions with small formatting differences, while setting them too low would cause spurious merges of structurally distinct formulas.

4. *Numerical validation.* For borderline cases, each expression is cross-evaluated on the samples of both candidate regions. If one expression generalizes well across both datasets, the two regions are merged.

5. *Iterative refinement.* After a merge, all samples are reassigned to the symbolic model with the lowest prediction error, and the local regressors are retrained on the updated sample sets. This process repeats iteratively until convergence, defined as no further merges applicable.

While the merging stage introduces some computational overhead, it provides a practical mechanism to consolidate redundant partitions when computational resources allow. Retaining similar symbolic expressions across neighboring regions is still acceptable when they remain interpretable and accurate. However, post-hoc merging enhances global compactness and consistency without compromising distinct regime behavior. The resulting Pc-SR representation preserves meaningful regime differences while yielding a concise, interpretable set of symbolic equations.

The implementation of the proposed Pc-SR framework, including the synthetic piecewise dataset used for benchmarking, is publicly available in the Pc-SR repository [20].

III. VALIDATION TESTS

This section validates Pc-SR by examining whether it can: (a) correctly identify regions with their associated expressions in a synthetic piecewise problem, and (b) recover the analytical CCT equations of two SMIB variants, one with a SG and one with a grid-forming converter.

A. Pc-SR: Recover synthetic piecewise benchmark

The validation of the Pc-SR framework was first conducted on a synthetic three-regime dataset. Six features (x_1, \dots, x_6) with sample size $N = 1500$ were independently drawn from a uniform distribution over $[0, 2)$. The target variable y was then generated according to region-specific symbolic expressions (Table I), with regions defined by axis-aligned rules on x_1 and x_4 . Additive Gaussian noise with standard deviation $\sigma = 0.05$ is applied to y to mimic measurement uncertainty. The planted functions combine linear and nonlinear terms, interactions, and irrelevant features, providing a structured yet challenging benchmark for Pc-SR.

TABLE I
SYNTHETIC PIECEWISE DATASET: REGIONS AND EXPRESSIONS.

Region	Region Condition	Expression	Samples
0	$x_1 < 1$	$2 \cdot x_2 + \sin(x_3)$	717
1	$x_1 \geq 1 \wedge x_4 < 1.0$	$\log(x_2 + 0.001) \cdot x_4$	408
2	$x_1 \geq 1 \wedge x_4 \geq 1.0$	$\sqrt{ x_3 - x_5 }$	375

1) *Pc-SR configuration*: A *base tree* is first fitted ($\text{max_depth} = 10, \text{min_samples_leaf} = 50$), after which the CCP path is traversed to retain the effective pruning parameters $\{\alpha_k\}$. To control runtime, $\{\alpha_k\}$ is sorted from large to small, and the candidate set is capped at 15 values. For each candidate tree, we train per-leaf SR models with a minimal operator set (binary and unary operators needed by Table I). PySR search runs for up to 50 iterations per leaf with a maximum symbolic complexity of 10. PySR’s denoising feature is deliberately omitted to test recovery directly from noisy data.

2) *Results*: A compact illustration of the Pc-SR workflow on the synthetic dataset appears in Fig. 2, showing cost-complexity pruning, symbolic model merging, and final regime extraction. The left panel visualizes the evolution along the CCP path, where progressively smaller α_k values increase model complexity by adding leaves. Symbolic expressions g_ℓ obtained in earlier iterations are cached and reused for unchanged regions, avoiding redundant PySR reruns and improving computational efficiency. The right panel depicts the canonicalization and embedding-based similarity checks used to merge functionally equivalent leaves (top) and the final merged Pc-SR model $\hat{f}(x)$ (bottom). For clarity, the figure shows two intermediate candidates and the optimal one with $\alpha^* \simeq 0.08$, which minimizes the composite score in (6). No simpler candidate (fewer leaves) falls within 5% of $S_w(\alpha^*)$, so α^* is retained. The score trace versus number of leaves across all candidates is shown in Fig. 3.

To examine the effect of score weights, we evaluated the full sweep, with Fig. 3 showing the MSE-, CVaR-, and LeafLp-only extremes and the baseline; intermediate weight combinations lie between these curves and are therefore omitted for clarity. The minima of these extremes mostly coincide with the baseline optimum at α^* , confirming that the selected partition is not an artifact of weighting. In this case, all objectives agree. In contrast, for larger power system datasets, MSE and CVaR may continue improving with depth, whereas LeafLp typically increases, as confirmed across multiple runs (across varying feature subsets, minimum number of samples per leaf and RDT random seeds). This reflects an imbalance across many small leaves, and its inclusion in the score guards against over-segmentation. It is worth noting that such cases are not shown here for brevity.

Post-hoc merging then consolidates leaves whose symbolic equations are equivalent. Leaves 1 and 2 yield functionally interchangeable expressions (after canonicalization and similarity checks), and are merged; samples are reassigned and the symbolic models are retrained on the combined region. After the merge, the condition on x_2 is effectively removed, since Leaves 1 and 2 collapse into a single region with a unified symbolic regressor. The recovered regimes and their equations match the planted ground truth in Table I. The end-to-end run completes in ≈ 3 minutes on a workstation with an Intel Core i7-11700 CPU @ 2.50 GHz (8 cores, 16 threads) and 16 GB RAM.

Pc-SR was also tested on independent evaluation sets: independent and identically distributed (IID) samples from the training distribution, samples concentrated near regime boundaries ($x_1 \approx 1, x_4 \approx 1$), stress cases at the edges of $[0, 2)$, and out-of-distribution points in $[0.1, 3.0)$. The model achieves high accuracy on all sets (Table II), with slight degradation near regime boundaries (small perturbations can flip membership).

TABLE II
PC-SR PERFORMANCE ON INDEPENDENT TEST SETS.

Test set	MSE	RMSE	R^2
IID samples from same distribution	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.011	0.99996
Samples near regime boundaries	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-2}$	0.137	0.993
Stress/edge-case samples	$6.9 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.026	0.9998
Out-of-distribution $[0.1, 3.0)$	$4.9 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.002	0.999999

B. Recover analytical CCT formulas on SMIB Systems

In these cases, Pc-SR correctly reduced to a single-leaf tree, yielding one global symbolic expression. Owing to space limitations, we directly highlight the match between the symbolic regressors and the analytical CCT equations.

Shared setup. A single generating unit—either a classical SG or a droop-controlled grid-forming (GFM) converter—is connected through a transformer and a transmission corridor to an infinite bus in *DIGSILENT PowerFactory* [21]. A balanced 3ϕ self-clearing fault is applied at the point of common coupling, and the CCT is determined from RMS simulations. Both cases intentionally adopt highly simplified SMIB representations to enable analytical tractability: the SG follows the classical model without automatic voltage regulator (AVR), power system stabilizer (PSS), or damping effects, while the GFM converter neglects current limitation and inertia, consistent with the assumptions in [22]. These abstractions isolate the dominant electromechanical and droop-related dynamics relevant to transient stability and provide closed-form analytical CCT expressions for direct validation of Pc-SR. Uncertain operating features, representing the main steady-state parameters that influence transient stability (e.g., dispatch, inertia, or droop gain), are sampled using Latin hypercube design ($N = 500$), with reactive power dispatch fixed to zero. Additionally, rotor angles are recorded to be used as training features in Pc-SR.

a) *Classical SG-SMIB*: The swing equation yields:

$$CCT_{SG} = \sqrt{\frac{4H(\delta_{cr} - \delta_0)}{2\pi f P_m}} = 0.1128 \sqrt{\frac{H(\delta_{cr} - \delta_0)}{P_m}}, \quad (7)$$

where $f = 50\text{Hz}$, H is the inertia constant, P_m the mechanical power, and δ_0, δ_{cr} the initial and critical rotor angles. We sample uncertain features: rated capacity $S_{\text{rated}} \in [100, 500]$ MVA, $P_m \in [0.2, 0.95]$ pu, $H \in [1, 10]$ s.

b) *Grid-forming converter SMIB*: For a droop-controlled converter (simplified model), [22] gives

$$CCT_{Conv} = \frac{\delta_{cr} - \delta_0}{m_p 2\pi f p^*} = 0.00318 \frac{\delta_{cr} - \delta_0}{m_p p^*}, \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2. Minimal Pc-SR illustration on the synthetic piecewise dataset (validation test): Tree evolution along the CCP path identifies the optimal partition (α^*). Canonicalization and embedding-based similarity checks merge equivalent symbolic models, yielding the final piecewise SR model $\hat{f}(x)$.

Fig. 3. Composite score $S_w(\alpha)$ across candidate α values (synthetic dataset).

with p^* denoting the converter active power setpoint, and m_p the droop gain. We sample uncertain features: $S_{rated} \in [500, 1000]$ MVA, $p^* \in [0.2, 0.95]$ pu, $m_p \in [1, 10]$ %.

Restricting PySR to algebraic and square-root operators (complexity ≤ 15) and supplying it with the same input features appearing in each analytical variant, the recovered expressions reproduced the exact structures in (7) and (8), with only minor deviations in the fitted constants (0.3% and 0.06%, respectively). Across runs, SR may return algebraically equivalent forms with negligible differences. For instance, in the GFM variant, it may select either δ_0 or δ_{cr} , since these variables exhibit near-linear dependence over the studied range (Pearson coefficient ≈ -0.998), leading SR to favor “cheaper” regressors using just one.

IV. DERIVING REGIME-CONDITIONED CCT EQUATIONS

Pc-SR is next applied to realistic systems to derive regime-conditioned CCT equations, following the procedure described in Section II.

A. Test Network and Operational Scenarios

The studied system is a modified version of the 39-bus New England system, incorporating equivalent models of Active Distribution Networks (ADNs). The dynamic response of ADNs is represented using the `der_a` model with dynamic voltage support enabled, in line with current and anticipated grid code mandates (corresponding to MA6 in [3]), while the remaining demand is modeled as a constant impedance load. In total, 10 transmission buses host ADN connections (Fig. 4). SGs are modeled as four-winding 6th-order machines with AVRs and PSSs (except for SG1). Generators operate within $[0.3, 0.85]$ pu active power (15% reserve) and $[-0.25, 0.5]$ pu reactive power of S_{rated} . Each SG is represented as four equal-sized units to enable disconnection scenarios, with the reduced nominal power analogous to lower plant inertia and increased reactance.

Fig. 4. Modified version of 39 Bus System

Operational scenarios were generated using Sobol sequences to sample load and DER injections, as detailed in [3]. Specifically, 10 loads and 10 DERs were varied independently within $[0.6, 1.3]$ pu and $[0.01, 1.1]$ pu of their rated values, respectively, resulting in cases with reverse power flow up to 75% of local demand. This base sampling yielded 1024 operat-

ing points, which were run through AC OPF (MATPOWER) across four SG capacity levels (100%, 75%, 50%, 25% of S_{rated}), giving 4096 scenarios. To better capture stressed conditions, an additional 256 snapshots were generated for the 25% S_{rated} case with loads in $[0.95, 1.1]$ pu and DERs in $[0.9, 1.1]$ pu. Of the 4352 OPF problems, 3754 converged and were transferred to *PowerFactory*, where CCTs for 3ϕ self-clearing faults at Bus 29 were determined via a binary search on RMS simulations [21].

B. Feature Selection for Pc-SR

The 50-dimensional feature set comprises initial rotor angles δ_i , SG kinetic energies $SGKE_i$ (defined as $S_{rated,i} \cdot H_i$), SG active power dispatches SGP_i ($i = 1, \dots, 10$), DER active power dispatches DP_k , and load active powers LP_k (with k indexing buses hosting ADNs). This choice reflects a balance between physical relevance and tractability: δ capture angle-dependent stability phenomena, $SGKE$ embed inertia constants, while SG, DER, and load injections represent the operating conditions influencing CCT. All quantities are in p.u. on a 100 MVA base, with angles in radians.

C. Pc-SR configuration

For the power system dataset, the Pc-SR configuration is adapted to account for its higher dimensionality and more complex dynamics compared to the synthetic benchmark. A *base regression tree* is first fit with depth limited to 10 and a minimum of 100 samples per leaf (due to increased dimensionality), after which the CCP path is traversed and the effective pruning parameters $\{\alpha_k\}$ are retained. To keep the procedure tractable, we sort $\{\alpha_k\}$ from large to small and restrict attention to the first 50 candidate values. Exploring more candidate alphas increases computational burden by allowing deeper trees, but it reduces the risk of being trapped in a local minimum. In practice, however, the procedure need not be exhaustive: once the algorithm reaches a partition that satisfies a predefined accuracy requirement (if there is such), the search can be terminated early.

Within each candidate partition, local symbolic regressors are trained using a deliberately constrained operator set. In addition to the basic binary operators, we allow only a small set of unary functions that are both interpretable and relevant for power system dynamics, namely $\sin(\cdot)$, $\cos(\cdot)$, $\sqrt{\cdot}$. Each PySR run is capped at 300 iterations per leaf, with a maximum symbolic complexity of 20 nodes, balancing expressiveness against the need for readability and runtime feasibility.

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

A. Partition Selection and Scoring

Candidate partitions along the CCP path were evaluated using the composite score $S_w(\alpha)$ under baseline weighting $w = (0.5, 0.3, 0.2)$. Figure 5 shows the score evolution across 30 candidate α values, together with the three single-objective cases for comparison. Although the candidate α budget was capped at 50, the effective CCP path for the studied dataset saturated after approximately 30 pruning steps, beyond which

TABLE III
GLOBAL PERFORMANCE METRICS OF PC-SR.

Metric	R^2	MSE (s^2)	RMSE (s)	$CVaR_{95}$ (s^2)
Score	0.999	2.3e-05	0.0047	1.6e-04

no additional distinct partitions were generated. Partition selection followed the 5% simplicity-bias rule (Section II-D), which chooses the simplest tree within 5% of the best score.

With a minimum of 100 samples per leaf, the selected partition (α^\dagger) produced an 18-leaf tree of depth 5, achieving excellent predictive performance (Table III). For reference, an XGBoost model trained on the same dataset achieved $MSE = 1.99e - 05$, $RMSE = 0.00447$ s, and $R^2 = 0.9992$, demonstrating predictive performance of the same order of magnitude. Pc-SR thus matches state-of-the-art black-box accuracy while yielding fully interpretable symbolic models, underscoring its value as a transparent surrogate for transient stability analysis.

In practice, a partition could be selected at the ‘knee’ of the composite score curve, where accuracy gains saturate. However, such knees are often ambiguous, as the decline may be gradual depending on the dataset, seed, or feature configuration. To ensure consistent and robust selection, the 5% simplicity-bias rule is adopted. This criterion consistently prevented overfitting and spurious partitions across repeated runs, while guaranteeing interpretability. Here, all regressors were unique, and no merging was required. Pc-SR completes in ≈ 70 minutes on the same hardware described in Section III-A2.

Fig. 5. Composite score $S_w(\alpha)$ across candidate α values (CCT dataset).

B. Interpretation of Regional Symbolic Models

As expected from physical intuition, inertia-related variables dominate the partitioning: in repeated runs the root node—and at least one of its immediate children—was an SGKE variable, most frequently $SGKE_9$, consistent with its role as the critical SG for faults at its high voltage bus. Because SG capacities vary proportionally in the current setting, SGKE variables are fully correlated; any SGKE split effectively encodes the same global capacity change. Beyond inertia, the RDT also splits on

active power dispatches and on initial rotor angles (notably δ_9 , occasionally δ_3), all of which are physically meaningful drivers of transient stability.

Across repeated runs of the framework with different RDT random seeds, there were cases in which partitions did not perfectly align with SG capacity regimes, leading to mixed leaves where SR models approximated capacity effects by including SGKE variables explicitly. While this does not invalidate the recovered surrogates—since they still track the local trends accurately—it reduces the smoothness of the resulting formulas and contradicts our initial goal. However, such cases were limited.

To keep the exposition concise, one representative leaf with a clear capacity-based separation (samples at 100% S_{rated}) yielding a compact symbolic law is illustrated. The corresponding region is defined as:

$$\mathcal{R}_{18}^{\alpha^\dagger} = \left\{ x \in \mathbb{R}^d : \begin{array}{l} SGKE5 > 8.12, SGKE8 > 21.26, \\ SGP6 > 3.79, SGP7 > 2.88 \end{array} \right\},$$

with its associated symbolic regressor

$$g_{18}^{\alpha^\dagger}(x) = 0.012167(\delta_5 \cdot DP25) + \frac{\delta_1 + 1.3266}{\delta_9 + SGP9}. \quad (9)$$

The model achieves strong local accuracy ($R^2 = 0.96$, RMSE = 0.0057 s), showing that Pc-SR can capture smooth dependencies in homogeneous capacity regimes. Equation (9) combines two interpretable components: a bilinear interaction $0.012(\delta_5 \cdot DP25)$ and a rational term $(\delta_1 + 1.3266)/(\delta_9 + SGP9)$. The rational denominator directly reflects classical transient stability related principles: higher pre-fault dispatches (hence mechanical loading) of the critical SG ($SGP9$) and larger initial rotor angles (δ_9), reduce transient stability margins (CCT). This aligns with equal-area considerations, where increased pre-fault loading reduces the available decelerating area. Conversely, the positive contribution of $0.012(\delta_5 \cdot DP25)$ indicates that increased DER injection at bus 25, when combined with favorable angular conditions at SG5, can enhance local synchronizing torque and thus increase CCT. While such interaction terms should not be interpreted as analytically derived physics-based equations, they reveal statistically meaningful relationships between variables and CCT within this operating regime and provide interpretable approximations of the underlying dynamics.

The fitted trends (Fig. 6) clearly reflect these effects: CCT increases with $DP25$, but decreases much more sharply with $SGP9$, indicating that the latter exerts a significantly stronger influence. While the functional form in (9) reveals the additive contributions of a bilinear term and a rational term, it does not by itself quantify which variables dominate. Relative influences can be formalized by evaluating partial derivatives across the domain, yielding local sensitivity indices. To quantify these effects, we indicatively report normalized squared shares $\tilde{S}_i = \frac{(S_i^\sigma)^2}{\sum_d (S_d^\sigma)^2}$, where $S_i^\sigma = \frac{\sigma_{x_i}}{\sigma_g} \sqrt{\mathbb{E}_\ell[(\partial g / \partial x_i)^2]}$ sigma-normalized local derivatives and d the number of features in the regional SR model (i.e., model in leaf ℓ). In $\mathcal{R}_{18}^{\alpha^\dagger}$

we obtain $\tilde{S}_{SGP9} = 0.774$ and $\tilde{S}_{DP25} = 0.0288$; hence $\tilde{S}_{SGP9}/\tilde{S}_{DP25} \approx 27$.

Fig. 6. Leaf-level relations for symbolic model $g_{18}^{\alpha^\dagger}(x)$. Blue markers show true values, orange markers predictions, with corresponding trend lines.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduced Piecewise Symbolic Regression (Pc-SR), a method that partitions the operational space of power systems and identifies symbolic functions for the Critical Clearing Time (CCT). The proposed method integrates cost-complexity-pruned partitioning with local Symbolic Regression (SR) to derive regime-conditioned surrogates of the CCT. The resulting “rule cards” combine region definitions (reflecting operational and physical power system parameters) with compact equations that reveal functional relations between features.

Validation on controlled cases confirmed the framework’s reliability: Pc-SR rediscovered the closed-form CCT in two Single-Machine Infinite-Bus system variants and accurately reconstructed predefined regions and expressions in a noisy synthetic benchmark. On a modified version of the 39-bus system with high penetration of active distribution networks, Pc-SR achieved high accuracy ($R^2 \approx 0.999$) while yielding concise equations aligned with physical intuition, revealing key inertia, dispatch, angle, and DER interactions.

While Pc-SR can recover exact analytical forms in confined settings, it does not guarantee unique physical law identification in high-dimensional systems with correlated features. In such cases, multiple algebraically distinct expressions may provide equivalent local approximations. The recovered symbolic models should therefore be interpreted as compact, regime-conditioned surrogates rather than definitive physical law-based equations.

These findings highlight Pc-SR’s strengths: (a) robust recovery of known laws under certain conditions, (b) principled handling of piecewise structure without over-segmentation, and (c) interpretability without loss of accuracy. Future work will extend Pc-SR to alternative partitioning schemes to eliminate mixed leaves, such as oblique or optimization-based trees, or evolutionary template-based structures (as proposed in [14]), which could better recover complex regime boundaries. In addition, improving computational scalability remains an important direction. Although caching substantially reduces computational cost, repeated symbolic regression across candidate partitions can become demanding for very large systems.

Preliminary parallel execution across multiple CPU cores (6 CPU cores) demonstrated runtime reductions of up to approximately 21%, suggesting promising avenues for further scalability improvements.

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